

Navigating Multi-System Interactions: A Nexus Framework for Sustainability Transitions Pathways

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1. Introduction

1.1. Multi-system perspective on sustainability transition: what for?

This paper aims to develop a multi-system framework, which provides a heuristic for participatory foresight processes to develop pathway narratives towards sustainable futures. It should enable to understand system change in the transdisciplinary context of a foresight process. It should help to reflect on the underlying assumptions of those systems in the present and to understand how systems must be deconstructed to develop new narratives. The heuristic should furthermore help to identify actors and stakeholders who should be involved in the participatory foresight process for those long-term matters. We, therefore, think that such a heuristic needs to include an ontology with complexes that can be made observable through different systems perspectives. The heuristic should also allow to identify of the nexuses and the measures which may make real transitions possible.

In Europe a need for developing transition pathways for multiple systems, which in the policy debates is framed as twin transition (green and digital) and just transition. The respective expectations are closely related to network infrastructures (energy, mobility, ICT, water), and fundamentally dependent on them (agri-food, built-environment and industrial manufacturing).

Although there is a claim to discuss twin transition together with just transition, under the headline of Tripple Transition, there is astonishing unavailability of linkage of this debate with human rights, in which universal basic services/essential services are formulated, also covering those network infrastructure related systems at that time (energy, water, electricity, - and now also ICT). We do not go into the just transition debate, but we would like to emphasise the link between network infrastructure as Universal basic services (UBS) (which relate to all humans and are not restricted to energy poverty, or unemployment challenges related to fading out fossil industries). Nevertheless, we should assume that the human right to UBS sets minimum requirements for provisioning services provided by SoP.

1.2. The need for a transdisciplinary, dynamic, and flexible approach to nexus dynamics

Governance fragmentation and siloed policymaking have long remained among the key challenges in designing sound pathways for sustainability (Estoque 2023; Liu et al. 2018). There is a need for reflexive and aware approaches to policy design, and explicitly for the language at the interface of multiple stakeholder contexts (Kujala et al. 2022) that can transcend the established dynamics and open up opportunities for democratic transformation pathways (Pickering et al. 2022) in a world of multi-crisis and deep uncertainty (Pahl-Wostl et al. 2023).

The past decade has shown progress in collaborations aimed at fostering sustainability transitions (Wahlund and Palm 2022). Such efforts however often face bottlenecks attributed to factors such as different values, frames, assumptions, goals and needs of involved actors (Raymond et al. 2023). They often resemble a selective focus on some elements at the expense of others paired with limited reflection on the implications of such choices (Royston et al. 2023). As specific policy-support approaches gain wider recognition, their limitations also come to the surface, e.g. integrated assessment models have become widely used within policymaking in the USA, UK and the EU but face limitations in grasping the just transition aspects (Rubiano Rivadeneira and Carton 2022). This may lead to what has been described as transformative innovation policy failures (Weber and Rohrer 2012).

Specifically, in the context of digital and energy transitions, the underlying complexity and multi-level nature of the interlinkages among multiple areas of effort may undermine necessary collaborations and the effectiveness of policy interventions and policy mixes (Bergek,

Hellsmark, and Karltorp 2023). The rapid development within the broad landscape of intervention possibilities and the need for identifying and utilising ‘deep leverage points’ (Schäpke et al. 2024) requires modes of collaboration beyond the conventional market mechanisms that can dynamically factor in new data, knowledge and perspectives (Clement 2022; Pickering et al. 2023), as well as discover new entry points and calibrate trajectories (Moallemi et al. 2024).

We use the concept of nexus, and more broadly nexus thinking as a platform and entry point for such an endeavour. Paired with an extended four-layered framework (presented further), nexus thinking provides much needed heuristic for building bridges across multiple contexts and from multiple perspectives, as a step towards enabling more inclusive, collaborative and informed transformations, while explicating the underlying complexity of issues at stake and allowing to make explicit the choices made at different steps in the process and their implications for actors involved.

Addressing the question of how nexus dynamics influence sustainability transitions, this paper contributes to the conceptualization and exploration of multi-system interactions. Nexus approaches allow us to connect different contexts and trace their mutual constitution. Examining the parallel and interrelated transition of the ICT system, the energy systems and industrial production and consumption systems, the paper delves into the various forms of nexus emerging at the interface of four layers and across five analytical dimensions.

1.3. Digital and energy transitions

Why the role of the energy sector’s transition is so central to the Great Transformation is analysed in a study of social revolutions during the fossil-fuel-based energy transition in the last five centuries (Fischer-Kowalski et al. 2023). It shows that modern energy use (mainly of fossil fuels) was driving industrialisation and that this goes together in most countries with revolutions and revolutionary events having taken place in the critical energy phase (CEP) of four decades. – i.e. it is to be expected that this time systemic change, triggered by a shift towards renewable resources– and likely the digital transformation, has also to be expected.

1.4. Contribution to the sustainability transitions research agenda

The paper addresses several key themes and issues within the sustainability transition research agenda as outlined in (Köhler et al. 2019), covering aspects such as understanding and governance of transitions, ethical aspects and reflections on methodologies. It further deals with more specific issues identified within the energy transitions research (Andersen et al. 2020; Brückmann et al. 2023; Foulds et al. 2023; Ingeborgrud et al. 2020), such as consideration of multi-sectoral dynamics (energy, industry, digitalisation) (Ingeborgrud et al. 2020), multi-system interactions (Rosenbloom 2020) (by explicating the interplay of different realms within the outlined ontological layers), their mutual constitution, as well as identification of neglected developments (Markard et al. 2021) through fostering inclusive and reflexive identification of relevant nexus nodes. We address the normative dimensions of transition research by explicating how the framework differentiates between production-consumption systems and systems of provision ((Plank et al. 2021; Schaffartzik et al. 2021).

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. In the next section (2) we present our theoretical framework for navigating multi-system transformations. The theoretical framework outlines our underlying assumptions and presents four ontological layers and five analytical dimensions. We use nexus as a bridging concept connecting different layers and dimensions, as well as heuristic for participatory foresight processes aiming at the development of cross-sectoral transformation

pathways. We further operationalise the framework through a four-layered model with a focus on the energy and digital transition (3) and apply it to a specific case study (4) of digital and energy transitions in the EU. We draw on this analysis to discuss (5) the broader implications of applying the four-layered model and the bridging concept of nexus to the study and design of multi-system transformations.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Philosophical foundations

The study builds on critical realism, as a philosophy of science that combines ontological realism' and 'epistemological relativism' (Sorrell 2018). This provides an entry point into different understandings of the phenomena in question across various strands of literature. We further draw on several interdisciplinary strands of research for developing distinct features of each layer, i.e. considering possible complementarities of different perspectives. This includes research on multi-system interactions (Andersen, Geels, et al. 2023; Andersen, Markard, et al. 2023; Cherp et al. 2018; Foxon 2013; Kanger et al. 2021; Löhr and Chlebna 2023; Mäkitie et al. 2022; Ohlendorf, Löhr, and Markard 2023; Papachristos, Sofianos, and Adamides 2013; Rosenbloom 2020; Sorrell 2018; Turnheim et al. 2015), Systems of Provision (SoP), and Social Ecology (Fanning, O'Neill, and Büchs 2020; Fine, Bayliss, and Robertson 2018; Fischer-Kowalski 2011; Haberl et al. 2021; Schaffartzik et al. 2021; Vogel et al. 2021), intersectional and pluralist scholarship (Flatschart 2017), controversy studies (Saltelli et al. 2020) and on the previous conceptual work on a four-layered conceptual model for analysing multi-system phenomena (Kubeczko 2023b, 2023a).

From a normative standpoint, systems differ by their purpose, and actors may tend to attribute different purposes to the systems in question. For this study, one key differentiation is made between production-consumption systems (PCSs) (as a basic component of mainstream economic thinking, commodification and logic of supply and demand) and systems of provision (SoPs), which is complemented with a specific ethical consideration and orientation towards both long-term sustainability and the provisioning of basic services to satisfy human needs as human rights (as legally, and often constitutionalised, right of all humans). In this context, it is however important to acknowledge the multiple values of nature beyond the provisioning perspective (Pascual, Balvanera, and Christie 2023; Raymond et al. 2023).

Table 1 Systems of provision vs Production-consumption systems

	System of Provision (SoP)	Production-Consumption Systems (PCS)
Allocation of resources	Is understood as the provisioning of services that are linked with stocks and flows of material and energy: Supply / logistics / service functions for wellbeing	Market forces (non-profit exceptions)
Unit of exchange (in the context of energy)	Energy as Universal Basic Services (UBS)	Energy as a commodity / tradable in different markets

Role of people in the energy system	Beneficiary of UBS, Self-servicing, system servicing	Household customer, “active customer”, self-generation
Rights of real and legal persons	Human Right for satisfying basic needs a limited to real persons and exclude legal persons, which nevertheless regulations ensure that businesses, particularly SMEs, have reliable access to energy at competitive rates.	Consumer rights to reliable and affordable energy
Relation to other systems	Provide input to other SoPs and PCSs dependent on energy services	Industrial sectors nexus – market relations of energy sector as PCS supplying energy logistics with households or other PCSs as customers
Relation btw humans and the environment	Sufficiency; Keeping practices within planetary boundaries	The environment provides energy and takes up emissions from energy consumption
Role of state	Guaranteeing energy services and access to the required infrastructures as a human right (based on how these rights manifest in the legal system and the institutional realm)	Sets rules for market actors and regulations for keeping monopolies under control; Plea for voluntary behavioral change (e.g. through nudging and incentives); Tackle energy poverty as market failure

We construct a hybrid epistemology, that encompasses an open-systems approach to reality where specific nodes are dynamically constituted through their relationships. To acknowledge the differences between the broader natural world and the more specific social world, we refer to the concept of social fields (Olsson and Jerneck 2018), aiming to grasp aspects that are specific to the actor layer (power, attitudes, frames, discourses) and the institutional layer (norms, values) in relation to other layers referring to aspects of directionality and transformation of the provisioning systems (Schaffartzik et al. 2021).

The phenomena occurring at each layer can be delineated, and yet the layers do not exist in silos but are rather subject to continuous mutual constitution, co-evolution, preservation and reconfiguration of relationships, and complex cross-layer dynamics. All actors depend on the shared cyber-physical infrastructure but may pursue different interests and engage in both competing and conflicting practices.

2.2. Layers

As a common ground for a hybrid epistemology, we conceptualise the four layers outlined below as ontological. They may be perceived differently depending on specific “techniques” (Saltelli et

al. 2020) for engagement with reality, knowledge systems, value standpoints, research methods and other factors that limit and direct our outlook. Movement beyond disciplinary silos has facilitated the exchange of knowledge and created avenues for collaboration across the layers. Beyond collecting relevant data points, obtaining relevant and actionable knowledge about layers requires an ongoing dialogue and deliberation about what is significant and what we care about broadly and in a given context.

2.2.1. Bio-physical layer

The Bio-physical Layer (CL) includes natural systems and the physical artefact of human endeavour. It provides a foundation for basic metabolic processes, thermodynamics, and chemical reactions. About other layers, include physical attributes necessary for the fulfilment of specific functions (functional layer), the storage of information about human institutions (institutional layer) and the practices of various actors (actor layer). Humans as living beings are part of this layer and may perform actor roles as individual beings as well as representatives of a corporation (or other legal person).

2.2.2. Functional layer

The Functional Layer (FL) includes complexes of provisioning functions and their interdependencies, drawing on the bio-physical foundations and subject to institutional arrangements and constellation of actors' needs and preferences. From a human standpoint, the functional layer serves as a meeting point for nature's possibilities and human aspirations, a juncture of what is possible and what is desirable, otherwise framed in the context of "safe and just operating space for humanity".

Humans engage with this layer through processes such as resourcification (identification, extraction, and commodification) of nature's elements turning them into the flows of goods and services, but also through practices such as nature protection, restoration, and rewilding. From a broader ecological standpoint, the layer is manifested through diversity, resilience, and long-term sustainability of nature.

2.2.3. Institutional layer

Institutions, or rules of the game, are constructed by actors but outlive them through their long-term existence. In the human world, institutions are represented by cultures, normative standpoints, governance structures, constitutions, policies, and other provisions that are accepted by a broad range of actors. From a more-than-human perspective, institutions are represented by established patterns of interactions among different species.

In the context of human-nature interactions, institutional arrangements set out specific rules and regulatory frameworks (e.g., on limits on extraction of specific material or protection of specific species and ecosystems from conversation), broader boundaries of what is desirable and acceptable (global sustainability goals, climate targets) as well as high-level concepts such as stewardship, safe and just operation space for humanity, commoning or conviviality. One of the key institutional arrangements in the focus of this study is the concept of universal basic services (UBS) and its legally binding manifestations in international and European law, and national constitutions, setting minimum requirements for provisioning services provided by SoP.

2.2.4. Actor-layer

Actor archetypes and roles (Wittmayer et al. 2017) are significant to understanding their impact. For example, they may be intermediaries, gatekeepers, leaders, accelerators and therefore

actors who shape the dynamics within and across other layers. The actor layer is strongly connected to the institutional layer through power relations, knowledge systems, culture and differentiated experiences of actors depending on specific institutional setups (May 2022).

In the actor layer specific features of actors are manifesting agency in the world. Humans may perform such actor roles as individuals as well as representatives of legal persons. This may include direct physical engagement with the world (at the bio-cyber-physical layer of which they are part) and through engaging in the flows of information, participation in discourses and frames, etc. between systems in the same layer. Actors engage with the word in a multitude of ways, participating in its continuous reconfiguration, shaping specific perspectives and constructing techniques that allow them to manifest their intentionality.

Actors may also perform different roles and have different degrees of influence on various aspects of reality. We adopt a fluid conception of actors, where actors may be seen differently by each other, perform different roles in different socio-political, spatial-temporal, and socio-ecological configurations, and may exhibit fundamentally different practices depending on specific actor networks in which they take part.

2.3. Nexus

Nexus has become an established concept in several fields of research, commonly dealing with science-policy interface, sustainability governance, sectoral interdependencies, and policy mixes. (Estoque 2023; Liu et al. 2018; Paleari 2024) . This paper develops an interdisciplinary understanding of nexus, considering the different ways to approach it and the multi-level nature of nexus thinking (Albrecht et al., 2018). While the concept of nexus has gained widespread use, its semantics are rather diverse (Botai et al. 2021). Here, we distinguish common ways nexus is conceptualised, acknowledging the contexts in which it is used and the intentionality behind such applications.

Table 2. Different uses of the nexus concept

Context	Use	Semantics
Philosophy	Category or attribute of reality	Nexus takes root in a range of philosophical currents, e.g. conceptualizations can be connected to the Kantian category of relation (Shields 2021), Whitehead’s process metaphysics or Barad’s concepts of intra-action (Barad 2007). This connects nexus thinking to relational turn within humanities, and specifically within sustainability science with a shift in focus on processes, experiences, places, practices and rethinking the language of sustainability transformations (van Noordwijk et al. 2023; Walsh, Böhme, and Wamsler 2021; West et al. 2020).
Flexible	Rhetorical devise	A wide range of sources across fields use nexus in its most direct meanings, as the intersection of two areas that create synergies or trade-offs, with limited further philosophical, theoretical, or methodological reflection. The concept may be more specifically used to denote a certain connection or interdependence, however without any explicit definition and with no or limited reflection on its characteristics.
Policy and domain-specific applications	Boundary object	The polysemic nature of nexus allows to use of it as a ‘plastic word’ or ‘boundary object’, where its definition is linked to the context it is used. ‘Resource nexus’ or ‘policy nexus’ (Paleari 2024) are examples of common cross-domain applications.

Interdisciplinary research	Analytical framework	Nexus has been increasingly used to denote efforts aimed at targeting disciplinary fragmentation and overcoming siloed thinking. In the context of various fields dealing with sustainability challenges, distinct analytical frameworks have been developed for the analysis of nexus, differing in scope and degrees of complexity (Ghodsvali, Krishnamurthy, and de Vries 2019; Haberl 2023; Liu et al. 2018). In those contexts, analyses of nexus are usually underpinned by specific theoretical assumptions, defined scope, and accompanied by a specific methodology and a process. Interdisciplinary uses of nexus are rather diverse and can serve different purposes, e.g. <i>stock-flow-service nexus</i> aims to “interactions between social-metabolic research, social sciences and the humanities by connecting to ‘practice-theory’” (Haberl 2023), while <i>resilience–sustainability–quality of life nexus</i> highlights “interconnected goals that are essential for human survival, development, and adaptation to environmental and socioeconomic changes” to “promote transformative governance and planning” (Estoque and Wu 2024). Thus, such interdisciplinary uses of nexus help to build bridges across the disciplines, but not necessarily across other contexts. It is possible to differentiate targeted uses in science-policy interfaces and policy mixes that are discipline-driven and context-dependent, and transdisciplinary process-oriented and participatory applications.
Transdisciplinary contexts	Bridging concept	Increasingly, nexus is appreciated for its capacity to serve as a bridge that works not only across disciplines, but across a broader range of contexts through a transdisciplinary lens (Ghodsvali, Krishnamurthy, and de Vries 2019). The complexity, multi-layered nature and diversity of nexuses are increasingly realised when nexus is used as a bridging concept (Estoque 2023). These applications draw on diverse ways nexus has been elaborated in social sciences and humanities, recognising the historical and political implications of the concept.

Within the context of EU policy-making, nexus is used as an “informed and transparent framework for determining the proper trade-offs and synergies that maintain the integrity and sustainability of ecosystems” (European Commission 2024). The European Green Deal and recent policy advances on biodiversity, circular economy and the climate crisis have been considered to resemble distinct orientations towards ‘nexus thinking’ (Paleari 2024). The use of nexus in such contexts is often instrumental, and the potential of exploration, and identification of new nodes may be limited to a rather pre-determined scope, e.g., the use of the concept of synergies is commonly concerned foremost with the questions of cost-efficiency, while trade-offs may be neglected.

Acknowledging its polysemic background, we use nexus as a bridging concept, that would support inter- and transdisciplinarity, bring together science and policy, and “strategically link different areas of work and practice” (Baggio et al., 2015). The suggested approach to nexus provides an entry point for co-analysis of critical nodes and opens space for thinking about

implications across the domains, rather than with a focus on a single interpretation and a narrow scope of issues. Applied within the four-layered and five analytical domains, nexus can be used for building bridges across contexts, allowing explicit relevant matters (Estoque 2023) mediated by the societal fields of different institutions and actors, making explicit both synergies and trade-offs from a variety of perspectives and facilitating transdisciplinary dialogues.

Based on the analysis of the literature, we suggest the following common characteristics of nexus for application in transdisciplinary and solution-oriented contexts.

Table 3. Key features of nexus. Own elaboration based on (Albrecht, Crootof, and Scott 2018; Estoque 2023; Ghodsvali, Krishnamurthy, and de Vries 2019; Haberl 2023; Haberl et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2018; Paleari 2024; Plank et al. 2021)

Concept	Description
Intersection	A nexus emerges at the intersection of two or more nodes that may have shared or different characteristics but interact in mutually constitutive way. That differentiates nexus from concepts like impact.
Interdependence	Recognition of complex interdependence of entities, processes, and systems, with the explicit aspiration of overcoming silo thinking (Estoque, 2023).
Normativity	Normative distinguishment of positive and negative aspects of the nexus, with aspiration for integrative thinking and reconciliation of tensions and conflicts.
Multi-perspective	Transdisciplinary and process-oriented application of nexus allows one to grasp different aspects of the same phenomena, e.g., synergies and trade-offs, positive and negative implications, and different actor standpoints. Nexus thinking allows for connecting different disciplines and stakeholder arenas.
Change	The dynamic interactions among the different nodes can change the underlying structures of each node, and lead to ongoing re-configuration of the parameters of different nodes and phenomena they represent. This may be manifested through processes such as co-evolution, spatial-temporal reconfigurations, socio-metabolic shifts etc.
Degrees of complexity	Nexus nodes can be represented by systems of different complexity, and new nodes can be formed through interactions of several systems. The level of analysis and specific composition of nodes will therefore influence the level of complexity of the nexus.
Contextuality	Nexus approaches are well suited for making explicit the context and scope within which certain phenomena are analysed, therefore helping to increase the transparency and credibility of participatory processes.
Directionality	Nexus applications commonly refer to specific purposes, goals and pathways.

An initial application of nexus to different layers and systems showcases a range of different concepts, which are sometimes related in meaning but also have their distinct scope of uses. Nexus therefore allows to connect the different nodes and to provide a framework for identifying and explaining significant interdependencies that have been previously analysed within a rather narrow scope. Recent years have seen a growing focus on the development of integrated nexus frameworks aiming to grasp a certain degree of system complexity (Estoque, 2023). Below, we go from more specific conceptualizations of nexus driven by certain disciplinary or policy perspectives, and towards increasingly more interdisciplinary and fluid ones that aim to better reflect the complexity of the world.

We outline an interdisciplinary typology of nexus, that includes system layers, and nexus nodes, accompanied by relevant analytical and assessment methods used within different fields of research. Nodes may interact within each type, across the node types, and nexus types, which can be also formulated in different layers of the system.

Table 4. Nexus nodes, methods for analysis and fields. Own elaboration

Layer	Nexus nodes	Methods	Fields
Bio-cyber-physical	<p>Natural structures and processes: Climate, Ecosystems and biodiversity, Air, Water, Land, Biogeochemical flows</p> <p>Physical manifestations of societal elements: populations, cyber- and physical infrastructures, artefacts (tools, means of production)</p> <p><i>Layer-specific axes: resources sink, ecosystem services</i></p>	Quantitative material- and energy flow macro-level analysis, agent-based modelling, Resource nexus models	Physics, social ecology, Ecological economics, Industrial ecology, Systems theory
Functional	<p>Provisioning functions relate to (A) people, as universal basic services for people: Food, Water and sanitation, Energy-related services, Housing, Mobility, Public Infrastructure, Education, Healthcare, ICT, and B) economic actors. In both cases provided services are closely related to and depend on network infrastructures.</p> <p>Industrial functions of production and consumption</p> <p><i>Layer-specific axes: resources-sinks, ecosystem services-human exploitation</i></p>	Material and energetic stocks and flows analysis, Quantitative model simulation, systems dynamic modelling	Physics, Socio-technical transition, French regulation theory, energy economics (mainly the domain of electrical engineers, other energy-related engineering, energy economics, energy policy, Sustainability transition research systems, Systems of Provision
Institutional	<p><i>Structural: governance arrangements, norms, values.</i></p> <p><i>Societal fields: laws, politics, social order, history, language, accounting practices,</i></p> <p><i>Layer-specific axes: urban-rural, resilience-vulnerability, rights-obligations, poverty-wealth, centralisation-dispersion, homogeneity-diversity. Social contract.</i></p>	Document analysis, institutional analysis, historical analysis,	Political science, social anthropology, Institutional economics, Cultural history,
Actor	General: agency, goals, needs, grand narratives, bearing of values, general roles, history of interactions, capacities, identity	Discourse analysis, Foresight, Qualitative methods for negotiation, deliberation and co-creation, social	Post-structuralism, Actor-network theory, social network theory, Micro-economics, practice theory,

	<p><i>Layer-specific axes:</i> cooperation-competition</p> <p>Contextual: interest, frames, contextual narratives and discourses, embeddedness in networks and specific roles and interests, inclusion and exclusion, representation</p>	<p>network analysis, Agent-based modelling, Helix models,</p>	<p>Sociology, Psychology, Institutional Economics, Theory of the firm</p>
Cross-layer	<p>Power-resilience-quality-of-life, stock-flows-service</p>	<p>Systems dynamic modelling, causal layered analysis (Milojević & Inayatullah, 2015), knowledge integration, hybrid epistemologies, multi-level perspective, dialectics, multi-paradigmatic modelling</p>	<p>Complexity theory, Transdisciplinary research, Pluriverse studies.</p>

The outlined typology provides the heuristic to analyse the Case Study. Based on these strands of conceptualisation, we introduce a comprehensive framework integrating and intersecting social, economic, technical, institutional, and ecological system perspectives.

Table 5 The intersection of layers and domains in nexus approaches: conceptual mapping of the growing degrees of complexity.

	No dimensions (descriptive)	Single dimension	Multiple dimensions
No layers (descriptive)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time nexus Space nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Space-time nexus Energy-matter nexus
Single layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actor nexus Institutional nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors-space nexus Temporality of different institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roles and capacities of actors in sustainability transitions Spatial perspective on sustainability transitions
Multiple layers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors-institutions nexus Biophysical – function nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors-institutions nexus in space Actors-function nexus Biophysical – function nexus in space 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stock-flow-service nexus Socio-ecological metabolism Finance-innovation-energy nexus Resilience-sustainability-quality of life nexus

3. Four-layer model for Energy and Digital System Transition

Here we will expand beyond the abstract description of layers, towards the more specific elaboration in the context of digital and energy transitions and the specificities of that system.

The two main differentiations as compared to the basic STRN literature here, and as outlined in chapter 2, are: 1) to introduce the bio-physical layer specifically (with its physical components and humans as living beings) and to consider this as cyber-physical realm in energy systems and

digital systems. 2) to differentiate between production-consumption systems (PCSs) and systems of provision (SoPs).

Table 6: Layers' expression in energy and digital systems

Bio-Cyber-physical realm	Built network infrastructures of electricity grids, power generation, power tools and artefacts, ICT network infrastructures, data processing, tools and artefacts for human purposes information and communication. People as users of energy and digital services, as operators of energy and digital infrastructure etc.
	Encompasses the natural environment: energy resources, ecosystem services, and sinks.
Functional realm of provisioning	Energy system functions are providing and securing energy services for people (as universal basic services like heating and mobility services,...) and access to energy for economic processes in industrial production-consumption systems.
	In the same way, ICT systems are providing and securing digital services, both for people (as universal basic services heating and mobility services,...) and for economic processes in industrial PCSs.
Institutional realm	Energy sector, and respectively ICT sector, specific institutional structures
Actors' realm	Incumbent and new actors and actor networks of energy and ICT SoPs at the actor's realm with specific goals, needs, grand narratives, bearing of values, general roles, history of interactions, capacities, and identity. Actors' interests, specific roles and interests, etc. are linked to the peculiarities of SoPs based on network infrastructures.

3.1. Bio-cyber-physical realm

The Bio-physical Layer includes natural systems and the physical artefact of human endeavour. In the case of energy and ICT systems, built network infrastructures of electricity grids, power generation, tools and artefacts to use energy, as well as ICT network infrastructures, data processing, tools and artefacts of for human purposes information and communication build the material basis. For this reason, we speak of a bio-cyber-physical realm.

People as bio-physical living beings are in this realm as users of energy services, operators of energy infrastructures, users of ICT services and operators of related infrastructures etc.

Furthermore the bio-physical layer, also encompasses the natural environment, with its energy resources, ecosystem-services and it is the sink to energy system-related emissions.

3.2. Functional realm of provisioning

Energy system functions are providing and securing energy services for people (as universal basic services like heating and mobility services) and access to energy for economic processes in industrial production-consumption systems. In the same way, ICT systems are providing and securing digital services, both for people (as universal basic services heating and mobility services) and for economic processes in industrial PCSs.

Digital architecture has become a basic element for energy systems and underpins the dynamics of the transition of the provisioning system. Digital information and communication as provisioning services are fundamental input factors to decarbonise energy provisioning, as is the energy SoP for other SoPs and PCS.

From a macro-economic perspective (political economy) there might be a benefit in a shift from a production-consumption system model (in which the pecuniary value chain is directly related to the flow (kWh) of electricity as a commodity and through “self-organising” market forces) towards the function of the energy SoP, in which value creation through services and the focus on transformative resilience might require further investigating into the value-chain nexus, logistic chain nexus, information-flow nexus.

In the current energy system, with strong centralised components functions are (a) mainly centralized energy generation, (b) grids for transmission and distribution of energy and (c) end-use. In the new energy regime, with an expected high share of distributed renewable energy resources, one might consider describing the basic functions more broadly as (a) concentrated and distributed energy generation, (b) integrated energy logistics including storage and conversion between energy carriers, (c) and services to people and economic actors which are dependent on the use of energy.

3.3. Institutional realm

Institutional structures include the public and corporate governance arrangements, norms, values, laws, politics, social order, history, language, and accounting practices which are energy sector, and respectively ICT sector, specific.

Institutional structures for energy and ICT have been developed differently depending on the legal systems, e.g., related to public and private ownership of the related network infrastructures and public and private corporations in charge of network operation, Also, several market institutions, and other regulated institutions for securing energy and digital services, have been established to structure the system functions at the functional realm of provisioning.

Laws and regulations play a role in how time intervals of the planning cycle impact x-curves, and how decentralization configurations are laid out and locked in.

Institutional structures (organizational structures and rule games) might shift from the main goal of supporting competition between incumbent actors through a mix of partial market mechanisms and regulations as a means of providing cheap energy towards the customers and allowing for short-term management of assets of monopolists (disincentivizing long term decision making by grid owners) towards institutional structures that incentivize long-term investment in hardware software and “orgware” (generational nexus) and encourage cooperation and allocation mechanisms which are speeding up the transition process (governance nexus).

3.4. Actors' realm

Agency of energy and ICT SoPs in the actor's realm is closely related to goals, needs, grand narratives, bearing of values, general roles, history of interactions, capacities, identity of incumbent and new actors and actor networks.

Actors' interests, frames, contextual narratives and discourses, embeddedness in networks and specific roles and interests, inclusion and exclusion, representation etc. are also specifically linked to the peculiarities of SoPs based on network infrastructures.

In the realm of actors in the ICT as well as energy soPs, we need to consider and engage a broader range of actors beyond those traditionally included across the policy cycle of energy and digitalization. From an ecosystem of incumbent actors and stakeholders, there is a shift towards new actor constellations including on the last mile of low voltage grid (grid-edge) and competing businesses on the medium-voltage grid-edge. New business models are enabled by digitalisation including opportunities for platform economy and cooperative models supported by digitalization). This includes clearer roles in developing transformative resilience (e.g. the state as insurer of last resort, critical infrastructure provision) and responsibilities in reaching the best outcomes for individual wellbeing (human rights) and the (national) economies.

3.5. Cross-layer model

We build on the assumption of downwardly influencing levels as in critical realist ontology. (Sorrell 2018). This means that all multi-system transition processes are understood as hierarchical in that they are based on a consecutive order of (a) available solutions, (b) innovation processes based on those solutions, which are new in the context of other systems, and (c) lead to new and successfully introduced solutions in these systems.

As in most observed cases, ICT-related multi-system transitions start with a digitalisation solution for which a technology is already available on the market. E.g., communication network services are needed for smart metering in the energy system. The ICT sector is for digitalisation is the Energy sector for decarbonisation. Some solutions, particularly related to electrification, are prerequisites for solutions in the mobility SoP (e.g. car-sharing with electric vehicles), manufacturing PCS (e.g. circular economy logistics) or for the PCS for the built environment (e.g. heat as a service).

Identifying nexuses between those systems should consider the ontological layers and the respective realm of each of the SoPs and PCSs.

Figure 1: Relation between energy and ICT SoPs and other SoPs and PCSs as spreading out across four layers

Source: based on (Kubeczko 2023)

4. Case study: Energy – Industry Nexus related foresight in Austria

4.1. Background and context

Applying the above-developed framework, we can explore an extended multi-system perspective as a heuristic for participatory foresight processes to develop pathway narratives and analyse Austrian foresight processes as case study related to decarbonizing the core of the energy system, as a SoP, and the industrial PCSs alongside the energy sector in Austria (AIT 2024; IV et al. 2019; Schützenhofer et al. 2023).

Examining the parallel and interrelated transition of energy systems and industrial production and consumption systems begins with a foresight process with Austrian actors and stakeholders in the research and innovation eco-system, which leads the Strategic Research Agenda for an Intelligent Energy System. (BMVIT 2016) And envisioned a Smart Grid Transition, from a centralised electricity system towards more decentralised and decarbonised grid configurations supporting the decarbonisation of the Austrian energy system. This already included a multi-system perspective on the interoperability of network infrastructures in the energy system and the role of digitalisation. Nevertheless, the aimed vision of transitioning towards an integrated sustainable energy system the status quo was separated energy sectors.

To make a step towards developing pathways, the most recent step was a combined modelling and foresight exercise by Austrian research and expert organisations. (Schützenhofer et al. 2023). The title of the project “Transformationspfade und FTI-Fahrplan für eine klimaneutrale Industrie 2040 in Österreich” suggests, it was a step from merely developing a mission-oriented STI roadmap towards broader policy messages for the transformation of the energy system as well as the industry system. Stakeholder participation in this project was limited to clarifying the project goals and informative meetings, this included not the climate ministry and the climate and energy fund as project owners and other research organisations in advisory roles, importantly social partnership representatives from industry, the chamber of labour and the chamber of commerce were involved. This ultimately led to a public event and presentation of the study and its recommendations in the presence of the climate minister herself.

4.2. Identifying types of nexuses for analyses

The focus in our illustrative case is on the energy transition of multiple socio-technical systems and the nexus between them on the 4 layers and between layers in the larger context of the transformation of our socio-economic and socio-ecological systems towards living well within planetary boundaries.

More concretely we focus on smart grid transitions and the dynamics between technological options/cyber-physical layer, cognitive frames/functional layer, the ecosystem of actors and stakeholders/actor layer, and institutional structures / institutional layer.

4.3. Focal analysis

4.3.1. Provisioning systems and value-chains

The human right to Universal basic services (UBS) sets minimum requirements for provisioning services provided by SoP. Nevertheless, the manifestation of related institutional arrangements might not be adequate in times of crisis. It should therefore be made more explicit that digital information and communication as provisioning services are fundamental input factors to energy provisioning, and that the energy SoPs are providing fundamental services for other SoPs and PCSs.

From a macro-economic perspective (political economy) there might be a benefit in a shift from a production-consumption system model (in which the pecuniary value chain is directly related to the flow (kWh) of electricity as a commodity and through “self-organising” market forces) -> towards the function of the energy SoP (in which value creation through services and the focus on transformative resilience), value-chain nexus, logistic chain nexus, information-flow nexus.

4.3.2. Institutions and Planning Cycle

As, based on new EU regulations the Austrian energy laws have been adapted to have a stronger focus on climate policy goals, institutional structures (organizational structures and rule games) might shift from the main goal of supporting competition between incumbent actors through a mix of partial market mechanisms and regulations as means of providing cheap energy towards the customers, and allowing for short-term management of assets of monopolists (disincentivizing long term decision making by grid owners). It is also discussed that institutional structures should incentivize long-term investment in hardware software and “orgware” (generational nexus) and encourage cooperation and allocation mechanisms which are speeding up the transition process (governance nexus).

4.3.3. Actor-network dynamics

At the actor layer a shift can be observed from an ecosystem of incumbent actors and stakeholders (with strong social network capital) towards new active actor constellations on household LV grid edge and competing businesses on the MV grid) and new business models (including opportunities for platform economy and cooperative models supported by digitalization). To build new social network capital (contractual/trust nexuses), those new actors would need to be considered, including clearer roles in developing transformative resilience and responsibilities in reaching the best outcomes for individual wellbeing (human rights) and the (national) economies (rights and responsibility nexus).

It might also be necessary to reconsider or introduce actor roles. One example is the tension in the different actor roles of the Austrian Chamber of Labour, which represents workers on the one side but also people as end users (provided with energy as UBS) in their consumer protection function. Furthermore, there appears to be no representation of owners of the infrastructure, which in Austria is mainly in public ownership.

4.3.4. Connecting the dots

The focus is on energy transitions in connection with the decarbonisation of industry and nexuses between systems at each layer.

For the bio-cyber-physical layer, a nexus is evident through technological change which manifested and led to revolutions in the social field. Future pathways might differ as technologies become more granular. (Grubler et al. 2018) And there might be a shift towards locating electricity generation closer to the grid edge. Time nexus might play a role in the shift from fossil fuels to cleaner and more sustainable energy sources which are characterised by higher volatility, requiring coordination of building new infrastructures (e.g. more storage, long-distance HVDC).

More emphasis might be required on the spatial dimension of the energy-industry nexus The shift of energy use via electricity as an energy carrier (e.g. in electrified household heating, e-mobility, industrial processes such as iron-steel and media-production processes like rendering in data-centres); at the same time infrastructures between energy carriers (heat/cold, green gas, ...) need to be more integrated.

5. Conclusion

The heuristic presented aims to provide a ground for building bridges across disciplines and stakeholder arenas to foster more inclusive, reflexive, flexible and informed collaborations that can navigate the underlying complexity of multiple transition priorities and aspects.

The framework may be used as a heuristic for transdisciplinary foresight processes aiming at the development of pathways, allowing the involved actors to approach and make sense of socio-technical, socio-ecological, and socio-economic dynamics in an inclusive, meaningful and informed manner.

From a sustainability transitions perspective, pathways towards twin- or triple transition as policy vision towards a fair and just smart energy system should build on a clear understanding of an energy system of provision. This shift in the heuristics from PCS to SoP provides a nexus between energy services, human rights and the SDGs.

Having a shared language and heuristic allows for the development of mutual understanding across research fields, connects incumbent and new actors' interests and contexts, and fosters dialogue and coalition building rather than multiple divides. It also allows to connection of multiple complexes of provision in different contexts making explicit differences in cyber-bio-physical dependencies, institutional arrangements, and actor networks.

Our proposed multi-system nexus framework reveals several key findings.

Introducing the bio-physical layer and cyber-physical nexus

Firstly, it provides deeper insights into the cyber-physical nexus between multiple systems concerning the related network infrastructures (electricity grids and information- and communication networks) and bio-physical metabolism (mainly energetic flows and stocks). It allows highlighting the mutual constitution of digital and energy system transitions, and both bear implications for the decarbonized provision of energy-related services to humans and industrial production. This might be seen as a contribution to conceptualising the “process of change in interacting social, technical, institutional and ecological systems.”(Turnheim et al. 2015)

Introducing Systems of Provision Next to Production and Consumption Systems

Secondly, it emphasizes the significance of adaptations in conceptualising the functional layer (and the consequences for identifying **institutional layer nexus**), which benefits from considering both energy and ICT systems as systems of provision, which provide energy services to industrial production and consumption systems as well as **universal basic services as a human right** to people (relevant for just transition). This differentiation is crucial for understanding as well as shaping nexuses at the actor layer (e.g. related to understanding mission models, and business models of actors) as well as the participatory mechanisms within energy systems and economies.

Thirdly, the framework underscores the pivotal role of the **actor layer nexus** facilitated and or hampered by interactions among diverse actors and organizations in driving change through envisioning, orchestrating, and fostering communication, thereby shaping, or prohibiting disruptive innovation processes and actor-network constellations.

Understanding of dynamics in multi-systems transition

The suggested multi-systems framework provides a foundation for the identification and analyses of specific nexuses, making explicit different layers of system attributes and factors in a diversity of constellations that allow to building of bridges across multiple contexts and unveil patterns that emerge at the intersection of multiple systems.

To highlight just some consequences of lack of adequate heuristics which might be concluded from the case study, are

- Unaddressed tensions between (and within) actor groups
- Missing actor and stakeholder experiences and interests (e.g. UBS)
- lack of realistic expectations about the feasibility of implementing suggested technologically possible options in the real world of multiple layers and different realms.

Contribution to transdisciplinary work and foresight processes

The conceptual framework aims to support the **development of cross-sectoral decarbonisation pathways** for energy, industry, and transport, engaging societal groups often excluded from strategic planning processes. By considering social-institutional-technological-ecological dimensions and nexuses in the reconfigurations of multiple sectoral systems, it holds the potential for co-developing more robust, resilient transition pathways and strategies, which are co-designed by relevant actors and stakeholders in participatory foresight processes.

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